

Integrating Social Determinants in Cardiomyopathy Management: Addressing Non-Adherence and Substance Abuse

Aveen Salar¹, Adam Manzoor Qazi¹, Carly Hubers^{2*}, Rahul Vyas¹, Kendall Conway², Victor Osio¹, Mahvish Renzu³

¹Department of Internal Medicine, Wayne State University & Detroit Medical Center, Detroit, MI

²Wayne State University School of Medicine, Detroit, MI

³Department of Internal Medicine, Wayne State University & Trinity Health Oakland, Pontiac, MI

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***Corresponding author:** Carly Hubers, Wayne State University School of Medicine, Detroit, MI

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ABSTRACT

A 41-year-old male with a history of drug-induced dilated cardiomyopathy, ejection fraction 10-15%, untreated hepatitis C, ongoing substance misuse, and cirrhosis presented with worsening dyspnea, leading to acute decompensation and cardiogenic shock. Despite aggressive management including inotropic support, continuous renal replacement therapy, and mechanical ventilation, the patient's condition declined, resulting in a decision for palliative care. This case highlights the importance of addressing social determinants of health, including addiction management and patient education, to improve patient outcomes in similar multifaceted cases.

Background: Non-ischemic cardiomyopathy often results from genetic factors or lifestyle choices such as substance abuse. The intersection of chronic illness, substance abuse, and poor medication adherence poses significant challenges in the management of cardiomyopathy, particularly when compounded by socio-economic factors and limited healthcare engagement. This report discusses the complexities of treating dilated cardiomyopathy within this context, stressing the necessity for an integrated approach that encompasses not only medical treatment, but also social and behavioral support systems.

Objective: To discuss the severe consequences of non-adherence in the management of dilated cardiomyopathy exacerbated by substance abuse and to explore strategies for integrating social determinants of health into patient care to enhance outcomes.

Keywords: Cardiomyopathy; Social determinants; Substance abuse

CASE REPORT

A 41-year-old male presented to the emergency department with acute worsening of chronic dyspnea, characterized by orthopnea and dyspnea on exertion. His medical history was significant for drug-induced biventricular dilated cardiomyopathy with an ejection fraction (EF) of 15%, post-automatic implantable cardioverter-defibrillator placement, untreated hepatitis C since one year prior, ongoing cocaine use, and recently diagnosed cirrhosis. Notably, he had been non-adherent to all prescribed medications for the past month.

Upon presentation, he was borderline hypotensive, afebrile, not tachycardic, and maintaining adequate oxygen saturation on room air. Initial investigations revealed a large right pleural effusion, cardiomegaly, and pulmonary vascular congestion on chest x-ray, with labs indicating lactate of 2.5 and creatinine of 1.68. He was admitted to the medical ICU for management of acute cardiogenic shock and possible hepatorenal syndrome.

Despite aggressive treatments including IV diuresis, inotropic support via dobutamine and milrinone, and mechanical ventilation, his condition rapidly deteriorated. He developed anuric acute kidney injury, worsening lactic acidosis, and coagulopathy indicative of hepatic dysfunction. A repeat echocardiogram showed severe tricuspid regurgitation and an EF less than 10%, confirming advanced cardiac decompensation.

Throughout his hospital stay, our patient's management was complicated due to his underlying non-adherence to treatment and ongoing drug use, which precluded him from consideration for transplant options. Eventually, palliative care was initiated after discussions with his family, reflecting on the patient's poor prognosis and quality of life considerations. He succumbed to his illness 13 days after admission in the presence of his family after palliative extubation.

DISCUSSION

This case exemplifies the severe implications of non-adherence to prescribed medical regimens in the setting of complex cardiomyopathy, compounded by illicit drug use and multi-organ dysfunction. The challenges of managing such patients are immense, primarily due to the intertwined effects of cardiac, renal, and hepatic pathologies, which are further complicated by psychosocial factors.

Clinicians must be vigilant in complex cases, such as this one, to integrate comprehensive care, including cardiology, nephrology, hepatology, and addiction services, to optimize outcomes and prevent such devastating outcomes. Moreover, this case serves as a crucial learning point for the medical community regarding the impacts of lifestyle choices on chronic conditions.

The tragic outcome of this case calls attention to the profound impact of social determinants of health, particularly in the context of addiction, non-adherence to medical treatment, and inadequate healthcare engagement. Our patient's continued substance abuse, non-compliance, and sporadic healthcare utilization reflect complex socio-behavioral issues that go beyond the scope of traditional medical management.

Addiction, a key factor in this case, significantly hindered this patient's ability to comply with treatment protocols designed to manage his cardiomyopathy and other comorbid conditions. His history of cocaine use and the resultant cardiogenic shock exemplify the need for effective addiction treatment programs as part of cardiovascular care in vulnerable populations. Incorporating addiction specialists into the care team early after

diagnosis, and ensuring continuity post-diagnosis, could provide the support necessary to address substance abuse, which is often a root cause of non-adherence.^[1]

Moreover, patient education plays a pivotal role in managing chronic illnesses, particularly for patients with multiple complex health issues. Educating patients like ours earlier in their care about the importance of medication adherence, the impacts of continued illicit drug use on their conditions, and the potential for drastic health deterioration could foster better engagement and compliance.^[2] Tailored education strategies that consider the patient's psychological and social contexts, and employ clear, compassionate communication, as well as providing relevant resources, could enhance understanding and motivation to follow treatment plans.

Primary care follow-up is another element that was notably absent in this patient's care. Regular follow-up visits with a primary care provider could have facilitated better management of his multiple health issues, provided regular monitoring of his condition, and offered an opportunity for ongoing support. Primary care providers are also in a unique position to coordinate care among various specialists and support services, ensuring a complete approach to the patient's health that can address both medical and socio-behavioral needs.^[3]

In conclusion, this case highlights the necessity of integrating social determinants of health into the medical management of complex cases. A holistic approach that includes robust addiction services, proactive patient education, and consistent primary care follow-up could potentially mitigate the progression of disease and prevent fatal outcomes in similar patients. Addressing these factors is not only crucial for the individual patient, but is also essential for the broader objectives of public health and healthcare sustainability.

REFERENCES

1. McKay JR. Impact of Continuing Care on Recovery From Substance Use Disorder. Alcohol Res. 2021;41(1):01.
2. Wu H, Lin W, Li Y. Health education in the management of chronic diseases among the elderly in the community with the assistance of a Mask R-CNN model. Am J Transl Res. 2023;15(7):4629-4638.
3. Shi L. The Impact of Primary Care: A Focused Review. Scientifica (Cairo) . 2012;2012:432892.